

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF MODERN RUSSIAN WORD FORMATION

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Annotation: In this article, the structure of the formation of words in the Russian language is studied. The order in which suffixes are added and their processes to form new word groups are also illustrated through examples.

Keywords: word formation, Russian language, morphemes, vocabulary, root, suffix, prefix, grammar, derivational nests, articulatory features, acoustic features, word combinations.

Word formation is one of the important sections of Russian language, it is interconnected with other sections of Russian studies. Studying word formation, you come into contact with history, and you start understand and appreciate the Russian language. This section helps to make our speech is correct, appropriate and expressive. [2] Not a single school the problem, in our opinion, cannot be solved if the student is poorly or insufficiently good and fluent in native language, including Russian language, since language is the main channel of socialization personality, introducing it to the cultural and historical experience humanity.

New words in Russian in the vast majority are formed according to ready-made samples from existing words, therefore of great practical importance is the assimilation by students word-formation means and familiarization with the basic word formation models in the study of the Russian language as non-native or as foreign. Understanding and knowing the laws of Russian word formation, students significantly improve their speech possibilities. Using known instructions (rules) word formation, students get the opportunity to model of these models to compose words of a certain semantics, as well as understand new words they encounter for the first time. The specifics of the word-formation system of the Russian language is the predominance of the morphological method of formation words. Relevant to practical grammar, both in receptive, so in a productive way are the skills of the ability to get the whole word from constituent units (morphemes). A clear understanding of the role and meanings of various derivational elements significantly increases the potential vocabulary of students, increases the feeling of a systemic connection of vocabulary and word formation, word formation and grammar, which undoubtedly has an important teaching value. Methodists rightly believe that speed memorization and understanding of new words depends on fame or the uncertainty of the structural elements of the word (root, suffix, prefix) [1].

The assimilation of word-formation patterns, should begin with a general idea of the composition of the word and through a long period of accumulation of word-formation patterns go to the systematization and generalization of word-formation means of the language. Questions of word formation should be in the field of view teacher throughout the entire period of study and skillfully be combined with the theme of the classes and complement them. At an early stage only the most commonly used word-building models with transparent morphological composition, correlating them with the studied grammatical

categories. Exercises should contain clear and understandable tasks with a clear division of the word-formation model and with samples for each word-formation type. Training should only be on productive formations.

For example:

Спортсмен (он) – спортсменка (она)

Армянин (он) – армянка (она)

Школьник (он) – школьница (она)

Читать (что делать?) – читатель (кто?)

Polyvertex derivational nests are formed in various ways: accent and lexico-morphological variants usually form nests of the combined type, derivatives which are equally possible on the basis of any of the options; phonemic variants can form two or more independent sockets with symmetrical or asymmetrical structure. Asymmetry in polyvertex derivational nests Russian language is one of the main properties of their structure and is of a different nature. It manifests itself at the level of the structure, nests in general: nests with two sub-cavities are possible, with two socket including derivatives with different derivational structure; with two sub-slots including derivatives as with different, and with an identical word-formation structure. The question of the device of the language, its structure, systemic connections between the elements of the language in modern linguistics is given a lot of attention, but nevertheless this question cannot be considered completely resolved. In principle, the systemic nature of relations between the elements of the language, the consistency of the language as a whole, the presence in the language of subsystems or "tiers" does not cause any doubts [3]. The situation is more complicated with the allocation of specific subsystems in the structure of the language, with the establishment of links between them. This information makes some general considerations about the structure of the language and in general, and, in particular, about the place of word formation in the structure of the language. These considerations are made on the material of the Russian language and are directly related before all about this language.

It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of system and structure, which are often mixed. Structure is the arrangement, arrangement, system - the nature of the relationship between the parts of the whole, its components. The structure of the language is systemic in its structure. The study of the structure of the language can be carried out from different parties, the researcher may be guided by different positions depending on what properties of the object are considered to be initial. But, following this or that approach, the linguist should not confuse them. It seems to us that when studying the structure of a language, one should clearly distinguish between "material" and functional approaches. With the material approach, the language is considered as a systemic device, consisting of tiered material units. The material units of the language include phonemes, morphemes, words combinations, sentences (simple and complex). These units are considered material because they are perceived by the senses; human (hearing or sight), these are the audible or read elements of the language. There are relations of occurrence between them: phonemes are included in morphemes, morphemes - in words, words - in phrases, phrases into offers. Each of the units has its own distinctive features, which are of a material nature. Phonemes have sets of differential features (articulatory and acoustic), words as sound complexes are separated by pauses, have their own stress, sentences are characterized by a special intonation, etc.

The material features of the elements play a very important role in the language. They allow separating from each other, highlighting, delimiting the material units of the language. Distinctive activity properties of these features is especially evident when studying an unfamiliar or unfamiliar language, in which one can learn to distinguish individual sounds, morphemes, words, sentences. But at the same time the ability of the material elements of a language of different types to distinguish themselves from each other is not independent. She is a consequence functional differences between these elements.

The general word-formation system of the Russian language consists of interconnected private word-building systems of all parts speech. Each particular system has its own set of methods word formations, the degree of productivity of which is not the same for various parts of speech. But, having its own specific features, private systems are closely interconnected with each other: as generating base for one or another lexico-grammatical discharge, words of different parts of speech are used, and the same word can be generating for words of different parts of speech. In modern Russian, the greatest activity in word-formation shows four main parts speech - noun, adjective, verb and adverb [4]. With the help of word-formation analysis, it is possible to establish, how a word is formed in Russian. It is at word-formation analysis determines from which word this word is formed, that is, the generating the word and the generating stem, it is indicated with the help of which word-building means it is formed, the method is determined and type of word formation. The original word, it is customary to call it the top, plays very important role in the formation of a word-formation nest, influences on its structure, semantic relations of cognate words in nest structure. It is included in all derivative words, determines their meaning. Problems of word formation of the Russian language do not lose its relevance for many decades, about as evidenced by the flow of articles and monographs on issues of Russian word production. It was during this time word formation took shape as a theoretical discipline with a certain object and methods of research. Difficulty and multidimensionality of word-formation phenomena, the possibility consideration of them from different perspectives led to the emergence various concepts related to the problems of word formation. What are the reasons for this? One of them, in our opinion, is an insufficiently clear understanding of the goals, vocabulary learning. The role of installation on the study of word formation as a tool for revealing the meaning unlearned derivatives and compound words when reading. This is especially important in an adult audience, where language learning takes place in basically as a conscious process. Another reason is the lack of textbooks on word formation and word-building dictionaries, as well as scientifically selected word-formation minima. Russian language programs for foreign students contain a certain amount derivational means, but they do not indicate that what speech skills and abilities should be developed in connection with study of this aspect of the language system. Russian verbs of motion, especially prefixed verbs, present a great challenge for international students. The complexity of aspect differences of verbs, the variety of verbs prefixes, questions of verb control, variability grammatical constructions - all this makes it difficult for free the use of verbs of motion in the speech of foreigners. At the word-formation level of the language, part of the vocabulary presented in a certain way organized with the help of word-building morphemes - prefixes, suffixes, as well as with with the help of generating bases. That is why when teaching Russian as a foreign language, the study of word formation verbs of motion is considered as a source of

replenishment students' vocabulary. Note the close relationship word formation with vocabulary and grammar.

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